

EXPLORING EUDAIMONIC WELL-BEING AMONG BANK CASHIERS: A QUALITATIVE STUDY

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ABSTRACT

In recent years, workplace wellbeing has focused on hedonic aspects, such as job satisfaction and stress reduction, by exploring profound dimensions. However, this study aims to investigate the eudaimonic wellbeing of bank cashiers in Faisalabad, Pakistan. The data were collected from nine bank cashiers through semi-structured interviews. The study employed a qualitative approach, utilizing a thematic analysis technique for data analysis. Thematic analysis yielded three overarching themes: the purpose and meanings of professional roles, organizational and structural challenges, and personal and social coping mechanisms. The study's findings revealed a high sense of identity, social contribution, and emotional maturity among bank cashiers. Participants also reported systematic challenges like stress at the workplace, restricted career opportunities, and gender-based constraints. Then, participants were applying resilience strategies, including emotional regulation and self-motivation. Furthermore, the overall findings highlight the importance of eudaimonic wellbeing in the performance of bank cashiers, underscoring the multifaceted nature of eudaimonic wellbeing. Finally, it is recommended that bank cashiers try to engage in physical exercises such as walking, jogging, and muscle toning. Futures should consider a large sample population from diverse areas.

Keywords: Eudaimonic Wellbeing, Bank Cashiers, Pakistan, Motivation for Job, Thematic Analysis, Bank Cashiers.

INTRODUCTION

Hedonic or eudaimonic characteristics have historically been used to define well-being. Hedonia, by definition, is a state of well-being that promotes the fullest enjoyment of life, steers clear of anguish and unpleasant emotional states, and fosters a sense of overall well-being. Eudaimonia, on the other hand, is a behaviour pattern intended to maximize human potential; in other words, it serves as a driving force behind human behaviour aimed at fostering a "flourishing life." The latter describes a life that is full of morals, meaning, and purpose, all of which

are considered the cornerstones of genuine happiness (VandenBos, 2015). Thus, if hedonism focuses on achieving instant pleasures and avoiding painful situations, in contrast, eudaimonia focuses on feelings and actions that promote long-term satisfaction and help an individual achieve their full potential, i.e., live a flourishing life. Well-being has been defined as the combination of feeling good and functioning well, encompassing the experience of positive emotions such as happiness and contentment, as well as the development of one's potential, having

some control over one's life, a sense of purpose, and positive relationships.

The hedonic aspects of evolving workplace well-being have been the focus of research in recent decades, as they encompass the broader and more profound concept of eudaimonic well-being, which is also linked to job satisfaction and pleasure. Eudaimonia is a significant concept in psychology, highlighting personal growth, purpose, self-realization, and authenticity (Ryan & Deci, 2001). Hedonic well-being is externally driven and short-lived, whereas eudaimonic well-being refers to the extent to which individuals perceive their role in contributing to a larger scale and find meaning in their work (Ryff & Singer, 2008). This paradigm shift is particularly relevant in service-oriented sectors, where human interaction and emotional labour are integral to job performance.

The banking sector in Pakistan represents one of the most structured and customer-facing industries, characterized by high workloads, strict regulatory oversight, and an evolving technological landscape (Naseem et al., 2012). While considerable attention has been paid to the financial performance and digital transformation of banks, the psychological well-being of employees, particularly bank cashiers, remains underexplored (Ur, 2024). These front-line employees often serve as the public face of the institution, managing daily customer transactions under time pressure and repetitive routines. However, they are rarely the subject of deeper well-being research (Hu, 2021). Cashiers typically operate under conditions of limited autonomy, high responsibility, and continuous interpersonal demands, all of which pose challenges to their psychological health and professional identity (Lundberg, 1999).

Although various studies have examined stress, burnout, and job satisfaction among Pakistani bank employees (Khalid et al., 2020), most of this literature is grounded in hedonic metrics and quantitative surveys, offering only a superficial view of employee experience. There is a significant research gap concerning the *qualitative, lived experiences* of bank cashiers and how they construct meaning, express autonomy, and pursue self-development in their roles. In the socio-cultural context of Pakistan, where collectivism, job insecurity, and limited mental health awareness influence professional life,

understanding eudaimonic well-being becomes both timely and necessary. This study aims to address this gap by conducting a qualitative exploration of eudaimonic well-being among bank cashiers in Pakistan, seeking to understand how these employees experience meaning, purpose, and personal growth in the workplace. The study aims to contribute to the growing field of positive organizational psychology, providing actionable insights for human resource strategies and policy development in Pakistan's banking sector. By shedding light on the deeper dimensions of workplace fulfillment, this research aims to reframe how organizational well-being is conceptualized, not merely as the absence of stress or burnout, but as the presence of meaningful work, self-realization, and psychological flourishing among those who often remain unheard in organizational research.

Literature Review

Eudaimonic well-being is increasingly acknowledged as a crucial component of overall well-being; however, little is known about the variables that affect people's eudaimonic development and maintenance. By combining previous studies on eudaimonic well-being in young people, identifying important variables and investigating practical interventions and tactics to enhance eudaimonic well-being in the professional setup, this thematic review seeks to close this knowledge gap. Eudaimonic well-being, encompassing personal development and exploration, is recognized as a tool to promote compassion and self-care, thereby fostering psychological health and self-compassion (Ryff, 1989). The foundation of eudaimonic well-being is appreciating the good things in life and supportive relationships with others. However, the significance of self-transcendent feelings, such as appreciation and compassion, binds us to something or someone outside of ourselves (Golec de Zavala et al., 2024).

According to Vittersø (2020), the hedonic approach is based on the notion that happiness and contentment are means to achieving well-being. The idea ties hedonic pleasure to well-being and emphasizes the importance of increasing satisfaction (Martela et al., 2019). Aristippus, a fourth-century BC intellectual philosopher, is credited with originating the view that happiness is the sole reason for life,

regardless of the cost. In contrast, existential constructs such as the flourishing of happiness and meaning in life are at the forefront of well-being. This approach views the process of discovering one's actual demons as a means to self-actualization and personal development (Huuta, 2016). In Waterman's theory of individual expression, eudaimonia refers to living in accordance with one's true self. According to this notion, engaging in activities that foster a person's skill and talent development advances personal growth and self-realization while also promoting eudaimonic well-being. In general, there are numerous areas where theories explain the overlap eudaimonic well-being including the significance of environmental mastery, pleasant relationships, autonomy, and self-realization (Waterman, 1993).

Ryan and Deci (2000) presented a paradigm for evaluating eudaimonic well-being that assumed the existence of three universally acknowledged basic needs. It is known as the Self-Determination Theory (SDT). This theory identifies the following needs for eudaimonic well-being: Autonomy is the ability to make one's own life decisions; it entails feeling that one's behaviour is self-endorsed and stems from personal beliefs and interests rather than being governed by external influences. Most, if not all, of our life choices, are representative of the common goal of achieving eudaimonic well-being, also known as eudaimonia (Javaid et al., 2023a; Ramzan et al., 2023a). Pursuing intrinsic objectives, meeting fundamental psychological requirements for autonomy, competence, and relatedness, and experiencing self-determined motivation are characteristics of eudaimonic well-being (Ramzan et al., 2023b; Ryan & Deci, 2001). Javaid et al. (2024a) examined the influence of mindfulness on environmental satisfaction among young adults, mediating the role of ecological identity, and concluded that the mediator played a significant role. Javaid et al. (2023b) reviewed the antecedents of employee well-being and organizations in Pakistan, explaining that two-thirds of studies treated the construct as employee well-being and studied it as a dependent variable. Javaid et al. (2024b) investigated eudaimonic well-being among young adults through a systematic review of influencing factors and outcomes. They indicated that different factors had influenced eudaimonic well-

being in young adults. Javaid et al. (2024c) investigated eudaimonic well-being among senior citizens, and the results showed that the general level of eudaimonic well-being among senior citizens in Pakistan was relatively low.

The study examines the impact of eudaimonic well-being on the performance of bank cashiers, acknowledging the challenges associated with their roles. Furthermore, by emphasising the importance of employee well-being, the research seeks to understand how promoting well-being can enhance job satisfaction, engagement, and ultimately, organisational success. All individuals strive for a satisfactory life.

Research Gap

Mahmood and Khan (2024) confirm that in Pakistani context the studies are hedonic aspects oriented such as job satisfaction, stress and work life balance however eudaimonic dimensions like personal growth autonomy and purpose are still unexplored particularly in a high pressure and front line roles of bank cashiers.

Research Objectives:

This study is determined to fulfill following research objectives:

- To understand how bank cashiers find meaning, purpose, and personal growth through their professional roles
- To explore the lived experiences of bank cashiers related to eudaimonic well-being in the workplace.
- To identify the personal, organizational, and social factors contributing to or hindering eudaimonic well-being among bank cashiers.

Research Significance

This research is significant since it illuminates the lived experiences of bank cashiers using the lens of eudaimonic well-being. The existing literature has focused on occupational upheavals, job satisfaction, and professionals' stress (Friganovic, 2019). However, this study contributes to the exploration of meanings, psychological growth, and purpose experienced by bank cashiers in high-pressure roles. This research is also significant in that it captures the complex psychological terrain among bank cashiers by identifying themes such as purpose in professional roles, organizational and structural challenges, and coping strategies.

The study offers insights into the social and cultural relevance of the eudaimonic theoretical paradigm, providing a more inclusive understanding of responsible professionals who are oriented towards social bonds, spiritual faith, and family responsibilities.

Method

Research Design

The study employs a qualitative approach, drawing insights from purposive sampling and semi-structured interviews conducted in Faisalabad, Pakistan. We analyzed the data using thematic analysis, following Braun and Clarke's (2006) guidelines.

Participants

Nine bank cashiers five female and four male participated in this study. There was an age range of twenty to forty years among participants.

Procedure:

Upon identifying the research problem, the relevant literature was thoroughly reviewed, and the study objectives were established, along with appropriate research questions. A self-designed interview protocol was then administered

following validation from an expert. Participants were recruited through personal contacts and resources, targeting bank cashiers (N=9) in Faisalabad. Adhering to research ethics, confidentiality was assured, and participants also signed consent letters. Data collection employed purposive sampling, which involves deliberately selecting participants based on predefined criteria relevant to the study's objectives. This method aimed to gather insights from individuals capable of providing pertinent data. Following interviews and data transcription, an open coding technique was employed to develop categories and sub-themes, enabling researchers to derive three major themes crucial for reaching the study's conclusions.

Data Analysis

Interviews were audio-recorded and manually transcribed by the researchers. A codebook was developed inductively based on repeated reading and familiarization with the data. Following Braun and Clarke's (2006) six-phase framework for thematic analysis, the researchers performed manual open coding by listening to the interviews and reviewing transcripts to identify patterns. The themes and subthemes are listed below.

Thematic Summary Table: Key Themes and Subthemes

Serial Number	Themes	Sub-Themes
1	Purpose and Meanings in Professional Roles	1. Sense of Contribution to Society 2. Self Worth and Identity through Working
2	Organizational and Structural Challenges	1. Workload Stress and Error Intolerance 2. Gender Based Constraints and Expectations 3. Limited Growth Opportunities and Recognition
3	Personal and Social Coping Mechanism	1. Emotional Resilience and Self Motivation 2. Role of Social Support and Faith

Results

The above described themes and subthemes derived from systematic manual coding, identify the patterns which illuminate the lived experiences of participants of eudaimonic well being which emphasizes on self realization, meaning, purpose, and psychological growth (Ryff, 2013). The analysis yielded three overarching themes and several sub-themes, each corresponding with the study's objectives:

a. Purpose and Meanings in Professional Roles

The researchers reveal from participants that they are valued and routinized externally and they are so satisfied by their service which directly influences them and their professional roles. Several participants were satisfied from external social and internal management satisfaction and they expressed that they always remained as a proud of community.

1. Sense of Contribution to Society

Participants emphasized the pride they felt in being responsible custodians of public funds. They viewed their work as a contribution to the economy, customer trust, and social order. *“People rely on me with their savings, their salaries, their pensions. It feels like I’m doing something important for them and for society”* (p. 4). It is aligned with the meaningful dimension of eudaimonic which provides satisfaction to the individuals and creates a sense of usefulness and autonomy among them. Even though, their under pressure sense of life does not depress them and they feel sense of proud by serving the nation wide community. It also elevates their job experience and they feel so ritualized in cash handling that they feel enjoyments in violent circumstances. Several participants noted that they had come to accept and value their role as a cashier. *“I’ve learned to accept my role as a cashier. It’s not just about transactions; it’s about making people feel welcome and valued”* (p.6). Bank cashiers mentioned gaining soft skills and emotional maturity through daily work interactions. *“Now I have more patience and better communication skills.”* (p.9)

2. Self Worth and Identity through Working

In the interviews, several participants revealed that their professional identity and career success are attributed to a sense of pride and self-respect. They claimed that their professional identity and the unlimited, powerful service they provide are a source of their soul satisfaction. Furthermore, they expressed that their financial independence and social recognition enhance their position in the social circle. As one individual expressed, *“When I tell people I work in a bank, they respect me. It feels good to be someone reliable, someone who matters”* (p. 2). Finally, they described their professional identity as a cause that fosters their self-worth, which echoes the eudaimonic goal of self-realisation. Participants reported that their job enabled them to tap into their inner potential and uncover their strengths. *“I just want to enhance my abilities or skills”* (p.7). They also explained that they had been identified through their work at the bank in the cashier position. *“This job has given me self-confidence”* (p.6)

b. Organizational and Structural Challenges

It associates to identify organizational, social and personal factors which hinder or contribute to the eudaimonic well being. The participants raveled their systemic limitations and organizational impediments in this theme which limited the well being of cashiers. They often are victimized by their psychological fulfillment and personal growth.

1. Workload Stress and Error Intolerance

Several interviewees complained about their extreme level of stress caused by unrelenting work scenario, long duty timings and zero tolerance at their mistakes. They were explaining their compulsion in front of circumstances. One of the participant reported *“There is no margin for error. I’m handling millions in cash daily, and one small miscalculation can cost my job”* (p.1). It is inferred by the conversation that their minor error can lead to serious and difficult circumstances to them. They can be victimized by disciplinary actions and psychological stress which further may cause their lives towards depression. This culture of fear and perfectionism is antithetical to eudaimonic ideals such as autonomy, creativity, and learning. The participants described their environments as rigid and high-stakes, leaving little room for self-improvement or innovation.

2. Limited Growth Opportunities and Recognition

The participants further expressed another major obstacle in regard to their well being and it was the lack of mobility. Many participants explained that they were struck in their service with hardly any expectation of their promotion instead of their hardworking. *“No matter how hard I work, I see no future here. I’ll retire as a cashier”* (p.7). Therefore, they are caused by the absence of self realization and fundamental component of eudaimonic well being. It was also the concern of participants that they were always lamented the lack of recognition from their supervisors. They were further demotivated and diminished from their workplace engagement. *“We are forced by the pressure of our seniors”* (p.9).

3. Gender Based Constraints and Expectations

The female participants described unique challenges which were faced by them. They were facing higher scrutiny, limited advancement, and

social expectations which were hindering to create a balance between their social and domestic responsibilities. They were concerned about their stagnant temperament in all the circumstances either work place or domestic environment. *“People expect me to do my job, stay calm with rude customers, go home, and be a perfect wife and mother. It’s exhausting”* (p.3). They also described that departmental patriarchy and cultural and masculine rituals exacerbated their emotional working by creating double burden and responsibility which had limited their personal and professional flourishing. These pressures detract from the essential eudaimonic goals of agency and well-being.

c. Personal and Social Coping Mechanism

In this theme the lived experiences were explored and identified by the participants and they contribute and hinder the factors of well being. By employing social and personal coping mechanism instead of all challenges and restrictions participants always sustained their purpose and protected psychological wellbeing.

1. Emotional Resilience and Self Motivation

The study also saw the resilience of participants in their interviews. They found their survival strategy in their development of internal resilience. They were viewed to be positive thinker, self disciplined and routine master. *“I’ve learned to keep my emotions in check. If I let every customer’s anger affect me, I wouldn’t survive a single day”* (p. 6). Many participants identified financial stability and responsibility to family as motivators. *Earning a steady income to support my family makes me feel responsible”* (p1). Participants felt moderately supported by management but stressed the need for better communication. *“Sometimes I feel overwhelmed, but my team helps me through it”* (p.7). Therefore we found through this resilient adoption the reflection of inner stability which is aligned with eudaimonic matters of virtue based coping and goal of psychological endurance. Many used the job as a stepping stone to build their reputation and expand professional skills. *“I’m using this job to gain experience for better opportunities.”* (p.8). The participants also conveyed that they are dependent on tea breaks, prayer time and family time break to cope instead of exercising. *“Exercise*

is a difficult task and tea breaks, prayers and family time are very easy (p.2,4,8,9) .

2. Role of Social Support and Faith

Participants highlighted peer camaraderie, family support, and religious faith as protective buffers. *“My mother reminds me that earning halal income is a blessing. It keeps me going”*(p. 9). *“My colleagues are like a second family. We share our burdens”* (p.8). Participants described daily learning from customer interactions and banking operations. *“I’m always eager to learn more... This keeps me engaged”* (p.1). Team dynamics played a crucial role in participants' coping and satisfaction. *“We all support each other... it helps us stay calm during stress”* (p.5). Several participants had aspirations to grow within the banking sector. *“I want to become a CRO in the future”* (p.1). Finally this social integration promotes belonging which is known as another aspect of eudaimonic wellbeing. There is a reaffirmation of values, construction of collective resilience and emotional nourishment which uplift the banking system.

Discussion

This study aimed to explore the eudaimonic well-being of bank cashiers through qualitative inquiry. Thematic analysis revealed that eudaimonic well-being was shaped by the purpose and meanings associated with professional roles, as well as emotional resilience and self-motivation. It further explores the sense of contribution to society, self-worth, and identity through work, emotional resilience, and self-motivation self-motivation, as well as the role of social support and faith; however, it faces organizational and structural challenges.

The first theme highlights how individuals seek purpose, personal values, and meaning in their routine work within professional roles, aligning with Ryff's (2013) concept of eudaimonic well-being, which posits that individuals strive for meaningful engagement, a purposeful lifestyle, and self-acceptance. Then, Waterman et al. (2008) posited that eudaimonia is experienced by individuals when they align their role with perceived social contribution. Similarly, participants have expressed their roles, which are socially oriented towards contribution and determined towards well-being. This finding is further supported by Steger et al. (2008), who have claimed that the meaning of work and its associations with psychological flourishing are

important. The pride of interacting with the public, achieving their confidence, and handling cash are high-stakes yet monotonous conditions that help individuals internalize their valuable role.

However, there is a contrast with the utilitarian model of work satisfaction, where economic necessity is more valuable than intrinsic meanings. However, the results demonstrate the strength of intrinsic motivation by suggesting that purposeful professionalism is a key factor, and they meet our first objective by understanding how bank cashiers find meaning, purpose, and personal growth through their professional roles. Our second theme is organizational and structural challenges, which encompass systematic handicaps such as a lack of recognition, limited promotion opportunities, gender-oriented restrictions, and excessive workload pressure. They hinder the realization of eudaimonic well-being due to environmental burden, which aligns with Imran (2023), who notes that the effects of job satisfaction are compromised by chronic stress and burnout among frontline bank cashiers, leading to professional weakness. It aligns with the second objective, i.e., the exploration of lived experiences among bank cashiers related to eudaimonic well-being in the workplace. This finding is further supported by Javaid et al. (2024c), who reported that the general level of eudaimonic well-being among senior citizens in Pakistan was relatively low.

Finally, there is a social and personal coping mechanism, which is aligned with Greenberg's (2004) stress and coping theory, where individuals develop emotion-focused strategies to manage stress when escape is impossible. It aligns with our third objective, which is to identify the personal, organizational, and social factors that contribute to or hinder eudaimonic well-being among bank cashiers. Additionally, many participants shared that they entered banking to build skills and expand their knowledge, even if they did not view cashiering as a long-term career path. These career-driven goals align with the findings of Khan and Javaid (2023), who noted that diverse work environments enhance motivation and well-being, which also relates to coping. While the psychological and professional aspects of well-being were acknowledged in the third theme of results, participants gave less

attention to physical health (Ramzan et al., 2025 a,b). Most reported relying on tea breaks and occasional snacks, with minimal awareness of the importance of physical exercise. The participants, in particular, neglected body movement and relaxation. As noted by Fatima et al. (2024), flexible work policies and health awareness initiatives could significantly improve long-term engagement. Although some participants mentioned enjoying breaks for prayer and family time, few practiced mindfulness or breathing exercise tools proven to boost well-being (Javaid et al., 2024a).

Conclusion

This qualitative study provided valuable insights into the eudaimonic well-being of bank cashiers working in a high-demand, customer-facing environment. Through a thematic analysis of semi-structured interviews, it was found that bank cashiers derive meaning, purpose, and personal growth from their work despite facing challenges. The three core themes that emerged are purpose and meaning in professional roles, organizational and structural challenges, and personal and social coping mechanisms. They demonstrate the multifaceted nature of eudaimonic well-being. These findings confirm that personal experiences, interpersonal relationships, and organisational factors have a profound influence on psychological well-being. Participants expressed fulfilment through self-discovery, skill development, supportive workplace relationships, and clear career goals; however, they also described challenges. Such elements align closely with Ryff's (1989) model of psychological well-being and self-determination theory, thereby enhancing the credibility and theoretical grounding of the study. However, the study's findings also highlight areas for improvement, such as the need for enhanced managerial support and increased awareness of physical health among employees. Given the limited sample and geographic focus, future research should include a larger and more diverse population to strengthen the generalizability of the results. This study contributes to the growing body of literature emphasizing the importance of employee well-being and encourages banking institutions to integrate well-being strategies into workplace policies.

Recommendations

This study was limited in its sampling to the nine bank cashiers and their specific age groups in Faisalabad. This study only displays the eudaimonic well-being among bank cashiers. Only males and females were included in this study. Future studies should be conducted with a larger and more diverse sample to enhance the generalizability of the findings, utilizing a combination of qualitative and quantitative methods to capture a more comprehensive view of well-being. We recommend that bank cashiers make time for physical exercise, such as walking and engaging in muscle activities. Future researchers should consider a larger sample population from different areas.

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